

METHODOLOGY OF USING MULTIMEDIA TOOLS IN TEACHING THE DUTOR INSTRUMENT

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the methodology for the effective use of multimedia tools in teaching the dutor instrument during music culture lessons in secondary schools. The study analyzes the issues of organizing the process of studying Uzbek national instruments, in particular the dutor, based on modern pedagogical technologies. The possibilities of developing students' musical hearing, performance skills and creative activity through multimedia tools - audio and video recordings, interactive presentations, virtual lesson plans and digital notes are revealed. The article substantiates the pedagogical effectiveness of multimedia-based classes through experimental work

Introduction.

In today's era of globalization and the rapid development of digital technologies, national music education faces two important tasks: on the one hand, to preserve the musical heritage of the Uzbek people, which has been formed over the centuries, and to instill it in the minds of the younger generation, and on the other hand, to find effective ways to teach this heritage based on modern educational requirements. Especially in secondary schools, the role of national musical instruments, including the dutor, in shaping the musical worldview of students is incomparable. The dutor is not only a musical instrument, but also a cultural symbol that embodies the spirit, aesthetic taste and historical memory of the people.

The modern student is growing up in an environment closely connected with information technologies. Traditional explanatory and demonstrative methods cannot always fully satisfy the interest of students. Therefore, the need to use multimedia tools in music culture lessons is becoming increasingly important. Through audio and video demonstrations, interactive presentations, digital notes, and virtual classes, the process of teaching the dutor instrument becomes more understandable, lively, and interesting for students. Such an approach develops not only students' hearing and performance skills, but also their musical thinking and creative activity. From this point of view, the development and improvement of the methodology for using multimedia tools in teaching the dutor instrument is one of the urgent issues of today's music education. This methodology allows combining national musical traditions with modern educational technologies. As a result, music lessons will be enriched in content, and students' interest, respect, and attention to national music will increase. This article analyzes these issues

from a scientific and pedagogical point of view and highlights the effective methodological aspects of using multimedia tools in teaching the dutor instrument. The mechanisms for using multimedia tools in teaching the dutor instrument are implemented gradually, based on the age and psychological characteristics of students, the level of musical preparation, and the conditions of secondary schools. These mechanisms serve to increase the effectiveness of education in music culture lessons.

Information and presentation mechanism.

This mechanism is aimed at forming initial knowledge about the origin, structure, performance capabilities and role of the dutor instrument in national music. In this process: multimedia presentations with parts of the dutor instrument, video clips of famous dutor performers, audio recordings of folk tunes are widely used. As a result, students' interest and motivation in the subject increases.

Demonstrative-auditory mechanism.

This mechanism activates the process of perceiving dutor performance. Through audio and video materials: methods of sound production, string playing techniques, sitting and holding the instrument are clearly and clearly demonstrated. The visual-auditory mechanism plays an important role in developing students' musical hearing.

Practical-executive mechanism.

This mechanism is aimed at organizing students' practical activities using multimedia tools. It includes: slow-motion recordings, step-by-step video lessons, and exercises based on digital notes. This process expands students' opportunities for independent practice, analysis, and improvement of their performance.

Interactive communication mechanism. The interactive mechanism provides active communication between the teacher and the student through multimedia platforms. With the help of questions and answers, tests, and virtual tasks: the level of students' knowledge is determined, performance errors are analyzed, and musical thinking is developed. This mechanism turns students into active participants in the lesson process. The mechanisms of using multimedia tools enrich traditional methods in teaching the dutor instrument and allow for a modern, effective, and student-centered organization of the educational process. Classes conducted on the basis of these mechanisms increase students' musical competence, performance skills, and interest in national music.

Discussion.

The use of multimedia tools in today's music education is not just a matter of technical convenience, but also a new level of pedagogical thinking. In particular, the use of multimedia tools in teaching national musical instruments such as the dutor serves as an important bridge between traditional forms of education and modern approaches. In this process, the question arises: do multimedia tools enrich the essence of national musical instrument education or extinguish its traditional spirit?

The observations obtained during the research show that multimedia tools, if properly selected and purposefully used, not only simplify the process of learning the dutor instrument, but also deepen its content. Through audio and video recordings, the student clearly perceives the subtleties of the dutor sound and minor differences in performance technique. The clear manifestation of technical details through multimedia that are not noticeable in traditional oral

explanations helps students to more quickly understand performance errors. At the same time, multimedia tools create the basis for the formation of the student not only as a listener, but also as an active performer and analyst. The student has the opportunity to watch his performance through a video recording and analyze it. This leads to the development of musical reflection, self-assessment and independent improvement skills. As a result, the process of learning the dutor instrument moves from mechanical repetition to a stage of creative research. However, it cannot be denied that there are some problems in the use of multimedia tools during the discussion. Limited technical capabilities, insufficiently developed digital competence of teachers, or excessive use of multimedia tools can negatively affect the effectiveness of education. Multimedia tools should be considered as an auxiliary and supporting factor, especially in national musical instrument education based on live performance and teacher-student traditions. From this point of view, the principle of balance is important in integrating multimedia tools into the process of teaching the dutor instrument. That is, technology should not replace performance, but enrich it. The emotion, national melody, and spirit of performance in playing the dutor cannot be limited to technique alone; on the contrary, multimedia tools should serve to deepen these aspects.

Conclusion

Multimedia tools effectively enrich traditional teaching methods by making the process of learning the dutor instrument visual, understandable, and interesting. In particular, step-by-step instructional video lessons and slowed-down performance recordings have become important in developing students' independent practice skills. During the study, it was found that as a result of multimedia-based classes, the process of understanding and eliminating students' performance errors has accelerated. It was determined that the effectiveness of using multimedia tools directly depends on the teacher's pedagogical and digital competence, as well as ensuring a balanced approach to the educational process. Only when multimedia tools are used as an auxiliary tool, rather than the main one, in teaching the dutor instrument can high results be achieved while preserving the traditional spirit of national instrument education.

In conclusion, the methodology of using multimedia tools in teaching the dutor instrument is of significant pedagogical importance in enriching the content of music culture lessons in secondary schools, increasing educational efficiency, and enhancing interest and respect for national music among students. The results of this study serve as a methodological basis for further scientific research aimed at improving the methodology for teaching Uzbek national instruments.

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